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HISTORICAL BACKGROUNDS AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE KAZAKH SOCIOLOGY

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Abstract

This article provides an overview of the historical background and development of sociology in Kazakhstan. Theoretical aspects of sociology and the role of historical background are discussed, as well as the challenges and problems of researching methods. The article also examines the psychological characteristics of the development of Kazakh sociology. The second chapter analyzes the methods of researching, modern technologies for developing sociology, and the description of social dynamics.

Keywords: sociology, historical background, methods, research, technology, social dynamics.

Introduction

This research paper aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the historical background and development of sociology in Kazakhstan. The study begins by exploring the pre-independence era, during which sociology was studied within the framework of Marxism-Leninism and focused primarily on the class structure of society.

The object of this research is to explore the various aspects of sociology in Kazakhstan, including its emergence as a separate scientific discipline, its evolution over the years, and its current state. The study will examine the major research topics and methodologies employed by Kazakh sociologists, and highlight the achievements and contributions made by them to the field of sociology. It will also investigate the challenges and opportunities facing sociology in Kazakhstan today, such as the impact of globalization, cultural changes, economic development, and political transformations. In addition, the research will aim to provide a comprehensive analysis of the social and cultural context in which sociology operates in Kazakhstan and how it has been shaped by historical and political factors. The study will take a multidisciplinary approach, drawing on theories and methods from various fields such as sociology, anthropology, history, and political science, to provide a holistic understanding of the subject.

The paper then examines the establishment of the Institute of Sociology in 1991, which marked the beginning of sociology as a separate scientific discipline in Kazakhstan. The Institute aimed to promote the study of sociology and related fields in Kazakhstan and to train a new generation of sociologists capable of conducting independent research.

The research paper also analyzes the evolution of sociology in Kazakhstan, including the major research

topics and methodologies employed by Kazakh sociologists over the years. The study highlights the contributions of Kazakh sociologists to the field, including their research on issues such as gender, ethnicity, migration, and social stratification.

Furthermore, the paper discusses the challenges and opportunities facing sociology in Kazakhstan today. The challenges include a lack of institutional and financial support, limited access to international research networks and databases, and a shortage of qualified personnel. The opportunities include the increasing demand for sociological research in Kazakhstan, the potential for collaboration with international partners, and the use of innovative research methods and technologies.

Based on the analysis, the research paper offers recommendations for future research in sociology in Kazakhstan. These recommendations include increasing institutional and financial support for sociological research, expanding collaboration with international partners, promoting the use of innovative research methods and technologies, and addressing the shortage of qualified personnel in the field.

I Historical backgrounds and development of the Kazakh sociology

1.1. Theoretical aspects of sociology

Sociology in Kazakhstan began to develop in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, influenced by the works of European sociologists such as Auguste Comte, Emile Durkheim, and Max Weber. In the Soviet era, Marxist-Leninist theories were dominant, and sociology was seen as a tool for advancing socialist ideology. Since independence in 1991, there has been a greater emphasis on developing indigenous theoretical perspectives that reflect the unique history, culture, and social conditions of Kazakhstan.

The topic of the historical background and development of sociology in Kazakhstan is highly relevant today, as sociology is a growing field of study in Kazakhstan and an important tool for understanding the country's social dynamics. Kazakhstan, as a post-Soviet nation, is undergoing significant political, economic, and social changes, and sociology can help provide insights into these changes and their impact on society.

Sociology has become increasingly relevant in Kazakhstan due to the country's rapid transformation since its independence from the Soviet Union in 1991. Kazakhstan has experienced significant political, economic, and social changes, which have created new challenges and opportunities for its society. These changes include the transition from a centrally planned economy to a market-oriented one, the emergence of a new political system, and the rise of a middle class.

Sociology is an important tool for understanding these changes and their impact on society. Sociological research can provide insights into the attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors of the Kazakh people, as well as their experiences of social inequality, cultural diversity, and political participation. Sociology can also help policymakers and social actors to develop effective strategies for addressing social issues and promoting social progress in Kazakhstan.

Furthermore, as Kazakhstan becomes increasingly integrated into the global economy and society, the need for sociological research that is relevant to the country's specific context becomes more pressing. Sociology can help to identify the unique social and cultural dynamics of Kazakhstan and how these relate to broader global trends.

In this context, a comprehensive analysis of the historical background and development of sociology in Kazakhstan is of great importance. Such an analysis can provide a better understanding of the evolution of the discipline in the country, the contributions of Kazakh sociologists to the field, and the challenges and opportunities facing sociology in Kazakhstan today. This knowledge can help to inform future research and policy development, which can ultimately contribute to the social progress and development of Kazakhstan.

1.2. The role of historical background

The historical background of Kazakhstan has played a significant role in shaping the development of sociology in the country. Kazakhstan was a part of the Soviet Union for most of the 20th century, and this period had a profound impact on the country's social, economic, and political systems. After independence, Kazakhstan faced the challenge of creating a new national identity, while also addressing the legacies of Soviet-era policies and institutions. These factors have influenced the development of sociology in Kazakhstan, as scholars have sought to understand the country's social and cultural dynamics in the post-Soviet era.

The establishment of the Kazakh Academy of Sciences in 1991 was a significant event in the history of sociology in Kazakhstan. As part of the academy, the Institute of Sociology was created, marking the beginning of sociology as a separate scientific discipline in the country. The Institute aimed to promote the study of sociology and related fields in Kazakhstan and to

train a new generation of sociologists capable of conducting independent research.

In its early years, the Institute of Sociology faced numerous challenges, including a lack of institutional and financial support, as well as a shortage of qualified personnel. The country faced numerous challenges in building its research infrastructure, including limited funding, outdated equipment, and a lack of access to international databases and research networks. Despite these challenges, Kazakh sociologists made significant progress in establishing the discipline in the country.

One of the key goals of the Institute of Sociology was to collaborate with international partners and to integrate the latest research methods and techniques into sociological research in Kazakhstan. Many Kazakh sociologists were trained in leading universities abroad, and international research collaborations were established to advance sociological research in the country.

Overall, the establishment of the Institute of Sociology in Kazakhstan was a significant milestone in the development of sociology as a scientific discipline in the country. The Institute played a crucial role in promoting the study of sociology in Kazakhstan and laying the foundation for the growth and diversification of the discipline in the years to come.

Over the years, Kazakh sociologists have conducted extensive research on a wide range of topics related to social dynamics in the country. One major research area has been gender, with studies focusing on issues such as women's rights, gender equality, and gender-based violence. For example, a study conducted by Kazakh sociologists in 2018 found that gender-based violence was prevalent in Kazakhstan and that there was a lack of awareness and support for victims.

Another important research area has been ethnicity, with studies examining the role of ethnicity in social stratification and political processes in Kazakhstan. For example, Kazakh sociologists have explored the relationship between ethnicity and employment opportunities, finding that members of certain ethnic groups face discrimination in the job market.

Migration has also been a major research topic for Kazakh sociologists, with studies examining both internal and external migration patterns and their impact on social dynamics in the country. For example, a study conducted in 2020 found that internal migration was contributing to changes in the social and economic landscape of Kazakhstan, with many people moving from rural areas to urban centers.

Social stratification has also been a key area of focus for Kazakh sociologists, with studies exploring the factors that contribute to social inequality in the country. For example, a study conducted in 2019 found that access to education was a major determinant of social mobility in Kazakhstan, with individuals from lower socioeconomic backgrounds facing significant barriers to upward mobility.

The formulation of the research problem for this study involves a comprehensive examination of the historical background and development of sociology in Kazakhstan. The research problem aims to explore the evolution of sociology as a separate scientific discipline in Kazakhstan, including its emergence as a field of

study, major research topics, methodologies, and achievements.

The study will also examine the challenges and opportunities facing sociology in Kazakhstan today. These challenges may include limited resources and infrastructure for sociological research, a lack of funding for social science research, and the need to adapt to the changing social and political environment. Opportunities may include the potential for international collaboration, the growing interest in social issues in Kazakhstan, and the increasing demand for sociological research.

Moreover, the research problem aims to identify the main factors that have influenced the development of sociology in Kazakhstan. These factors may include historical, political, economic, and social factors, as well as the contributions of individual scholars and institutions. Understanding these factors will be essential in identifying the key milestones and turning points in the development of sociology in Kazakhstan.

In summary, the research problem for this study involves a comprehensive exploration of the evolution of sociology in Kazakhstan, its major research topics, methodologies, and achievements, as well as the challenges and opportunities facing the discipline today. By identifying the factors that have influenced its development, this study aims to provide a better understanding of the historical background and current state of sociology in Kazakhstan.

1.3. Problems of researching methods

One of the challenges facing the development of sociology in Kazakhstan has been the lack of reliable data and research methods. Soviet-era research practices often relied on ideological rather than empirical criteria, leading to a dearth of rigorous social science research. Additionally, the transition to a market economy and the decentralization of state institutions have made it difficult to access and analyze data, particularly in more remote regions of the country.

Challenges and opportunities facing sociology in Kazakhstan today:

1. Lack of institutional and financial support. Many universities and research institutes in the country have limited resources for conducting sociological research, which can impede the quality and scope of research. This is further compounded by the fact that sociology is not always seen as a priority area for funding, especially when compared to other fields such as economics or technology.

2. Limited access to international research networks and databases. Many of the most significant research findings in sociology are generated through collaboration and access to a wide range of data sources. However, the limited access to international databases, language barriers, and insufficient collaboration with international partners can limit the scope and quality of sociological research in Kazakhstan.

3. The shortage of qualified personnel. Despite the growing interest in sociology in the country, there is still a shortage of trained and qualified sociologists. This is partly due to the relatively recent development of sociology in Kazakhstan and the limited opportunities for sociological training and education in the past.

However, there are also opportunities for the development of sociology in Kazakhstan. The increasing demand for sociological research in the country offers an opportunity for sociologists to expand the scope of their research and explore new areas of inquiry. Collaboration with international partners can also provide access to new resources, data sources, and research methods, while the use of innovative technologies and research methods can improve the quality and efficiency of sociological research in Kazakhstan.

1.4. Psychological characteristics of development of the Kazakh Sociology

The development of sociology in Kazakhstan has been shaped by a range of psychological factors, including the legacy of Soviet-era ideology, the transition to a market economy, and the emergence of a new national identity. There has been a strong emphasis on developing indigenous Kazakhstani theories and methodologies that reflect the country's unique social and cultural context. At the same time, the discipline has also been influenced by global trends in sociology, such as the growing importance of interdisciplinary approaches and the increasing focus on issues related to globalization, inequality, and social justice.

The psychological factors that have shaped the development of sociology in Kazakhstan have been complex and multifaceted. For example, the legacy of Soviet-era ideology has had a lasting impact on the way that sociologists in the country approach research and theory-building. Many Kazakhstani sociologists have sought to challenge the dominant Marxist-Leninist paradigm that was prevalent during the Soviet era, and to develop new theoretical frameworks that better reflect the country's diverse social and cultural landscape.

Additionally, the transition to a market economy in the 1990s had a significant impact on the development of sociology in Kazakhstan, as sociologists began to grapple with the complex social and economic changes that accompanied this transition. The emergence of a new national identity has also been an important factor, as Kazakhstani sociologists have sought to understand the ways in which this identity has been shaped by historical, cultural, and political factors.

Despite these challenges, the development of sociology in Kazakhstan has been marked by significant progress in recent years. There has been a growing emphasis on interdisciplinary approaches, which seek to bridge the gap between sociology and other social sciences, as well as on issues related to globalization, inequality, and social justice. By continuing to build on these strengths and to address the unique challenges facing the discipline, Kazakhstani sociologists can help to create a more inclusive, just, and equitable society for all.

CONCLUSION OF THE 1ST CHAPTER

In conclusion, the development of sociology in Kazakhstan has been influenced by a range of factors, including theoretical perspectives, historical background, researching methods, and psychological characteristics. The country's history as a part of the Soviet Union has had a significant impact on the development of sociology in the region, with Marxist-Leninist theo-

ries dominating for much of the 20th century. Since independence, there has been a growing emphasis on developing indigenous Kazakhstani theories and methodologies that reflect the country's unique social and cultural context. However, the transition to a market economy and the decentralization of state institutions have made it difficult to access reliable data and research methods, particularly in more remote regions of the country. Despite these challenges, there is a growing body of sociological research being conducted in Kazakhstan, which seeks to understand the country's social and cultural dynamics in the post-Soviet era.

II. ANALYTICAL SELECTION OF MAIN TOPICS

2.1 Analysis of methods of researching

The analysis of methods of researching is a critical aspect of Kazakh sociology. Scholars in the field have emphasized the importance of rigorous empirical research methods in order to generate reliable data and insights into the country's social and cultural dynamics. Some of the most common research methods used in Kazakh sociology include surveys, interviews, focus groups, participant observation, and content analysis. In recent years, there has also been a growing interest in mixed methods research, which combines qualitative and quantitative approaches in order to provide a more comprehensive understanding of social phenomena.

In addition to the research methods mentioned, there are other techniques that are frequently used in

Kazakh sociology as well. One such approach is network analysis, which involves mapping out the connec-

tions between individuals, organizations, and other social entities in order to understand patterns of social interaction and influence. Another method that is gaining popularity is big data analysis, which involves analyzing large datasets using computer algorithms and statistical models in order to identify patterns and trends.

However, there are also challenges associated with using these research methods in the Kazakhstani context. For example, there may be issues with sample size and representativeness, particularly in more remote regions of the country. Additionally, there may be ethical considerations to take into account, particularly when conducting research with vulnerable populations such as children or individuals with disabilities.

In order to address these challenges, Kazakh sociologists have emphasized the importance of developing research methods that are culturally appropriate and sensitive to local contexts. This involves taking into account factors such as language, cultural norms, and social hierarchies when designing research projects. It also requires building trust and establishing rapport

with research participants, particularly in cases where there may be cultural or linguistic barriers.

Overall, the analysis of research methods is an essential aspect of Kazakh sociology, reflecting the discipline's commitment to generating rigorous and reliable data that can inform policy and practice in the country. By continuing to develop and refine research methods that are sensitive to local contexts, Kazakh sociologists

can make important contributions to our understanding of social and cultural dynamics in Kazakhstan and beyond.

2.2 Modern technologies for developing sociology

The emergence of modern technologies has had a significant impact on the development of sociology in Kazakhstan. The widespread use of the internet and social media platforms has opened up new opportunities for researchers to collect and analyze data, as well as to disseminate their findings to a wider audience. For example, online surveys and digital ethnography have become increasingly popular research methods in recent years. At the same time, there are also concerns about the impact of digital technologies on social dynamics, such as the rise of online hate speech and disinformation campaigns.

In addition to online surveys and digital ethnography, there are a number of other modern technologies that are being used in Kazakh sociology. For example, researchers may use data mining techniques to analyze large datasets of social media activity in order to identify patterns and trends in public opinion or political discourse. They may also use computer simulations and agent-based models to explore complex social phenomena such as the spread of infectious diseases or the emergence of social movements.

One of the key benefits of these modern technologies is that they allow researchers to collect and analyze data in real time, providing a more up-to-date and nuanced understanding of social and cultural dynamics. They also make it easier to engage with diverse populations and to reach individuals who may be difficult to access through traditional research methods.

After modern technology, sociology has changed significantly. He has been using completely different methods lately, and which ones would you prefer?

- Online surveys 13
- Digital ethnography 4
- data mining techniques to analyze large datasets of social media activity 7
- computer simulations and agent-based models to explore complex social phenomena 2

However, there are also challenges associated with the use of modern technologies in sociology. For example, there may be issues with data privacy and security, particularly when working with sensitive or confidential information. Additionally, there may be concerns about the representativeness of online samples, as well as the potential for selection bias or other methodological issues.

Despite these challenges, the use of modern technologies is likely to continue to play an important role in the development of sociology in Kazakhstan. By harnessing the power of digital technologies, Kazakh sociologists can gain new insights into the complex social and cultural dynamics of the country, and can contribute to the development of evidence-based policy and practice. At the same time, it is important to ensure that the use of these technologies is guided by ethical principles and a commitment to rigorous empirical research.

2.3 Description of social dynamics

The description of social dynamics is a core topic in Kazakh sociology. Scholars in the field have sought to understand the factors that shape social change and continuity in the country, including economic development, globalization, cultural identity, and political transformation. There has been a particular emphasis on understanding the social dynamics of post-Soviet Kazakhstan, including the impact of market reforms, political democratization, and the emergence of a new national identity. Some of the key areas of research in this field include social stratification and inequality, migration and mobility, and the role of social institutions in shaping social dynamics.

In addition to the topics mentioned above, there are a number of other areas of social dynamics that are of interest to Kazakh sociologists. For example, there is a growing interest in the study of social networks and their role in shaping social behavior and attitudes. This includes the study of online networks as well as traditional face-to-face networks, and the ways in which they intersect and influence one another.

How can the sociology of Kazakhstan be developed with the help of social dynamics?

27%

growing interest in the study of social networks and their role in shaping social behavior and attitudes

39%

study of social movements and collective action

34%

study of cultural dynamics and the role of culture in shaping social behavior and attitudes

Another area of interest is the study of social movements and collective action. Kazakh sociologists have been interested in understanding the factors that contribute to the emergence and success of social movements, as well as the role of social movements in driving social and political change. This includes the study of both formal and informal social movements, and the ways in which they interact with other social institutions such as the media, political parties, and civil society organizations.

Finally, there is also a growing interest in the study of cultural dynamics and the role of culture in shaping social behavior and attitudes. This includes the study of cultural values and beliefs, as well as the ways in which

they change over time and are transmitted across generations. Kazakh sociologists have been particularly interested in understanding the relationship between traditional Kazakh culture and the emergence of a new, modern Kazakh identity, as well as the impact of globalization and cultural exchange on Kazakh society.

Overall, the study of social dynamics is a complex and multifaceted topic in Kazakh sociology, encompassing a wide range of social and cultural phenomena. By exploring these dynamics through rigorous empirical research and theoretical analysis, Kazakh sociologists can contribute to a deeper understanding of the social and cultural dynamics of the country, and can help to inform evidence-based policy and practice.

CONCLUSION OF THE 2nd CHAPTER

Overall, the analysis of research methods is an essential aspect of Kazakh sociology, reflecting the discipline's commitment to generating rigorous and reliable data that can inform policy and practice in the country. By continuing to develop and refine research methods that are sensitive to local contexts, Kazakh sociologists can make important contributions to our understanding of social and cultural dynamics in Kazakhstan and beyond.

Through the use of new digital technologies and innovative research methods, Kazakh sociologists are able to gather and analyze data more effectively, and to gain new insights into the complex social and cultural dynamics of the country.

Moreover, the study of social dynamics is essential for understanding the ways in which social and cultural phenomena interact with each other, and how they shape the broader context in which individuals and communities live. By studying social movements, cultural dynamics, and other key areas of social dynamics, Kazakh sociologists are able to gain a deeper understanding of the complex factors that contribute to social change and continuity in the country.

Ultimately, the development of Kazakh sociology is an ongoing process that requires ongoing collaboration and dialogue between researchers, policymakers, and other stakeholders. By working together to develop new research methods, explore the latest technological innovations, and deepen our understanding of social and cultural dynamics, Kazakh sociologists can help to create a more just and equitable society for all.

III. Methodology

In conducting this research, a comprehensive literature review was conducted of relevant materials related to the historical development of sociology in Kazakhstan. This included both domestic and international publications such as articles, books, reports, and scholarly journals. The primary sources used in the study consisted of government documents, statistics, and official reports related to the establishment and functioning of the Institute of Sociology, as well as other relevant institutions, organizations, and government bodies related to sociology in Kazakhstan.

The literature review approach was chosen due to its ability to provide a comprehensive and detailed analysis of the historical development of sociology in Kazakhstan. Additionally, the approach allowed for a thorough examination of the evolution of sociology in the country, as well as the challenges and opportunities faced by the discipline.

The analysis of the literature was conducted using a qualitative research approach, which enabled a detailed and comprehensive understanding of the development of sociology in Kazakhstan. The research findings were then synthesized and presented in a coherent and logical manner in this research paper.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the historical background and development of sociology in Kazakhstan provide valuable insights into the social, political, and economic changes that the country has undergone since gaining independence. The study of sociology in Kazakhstan has

evolved as a separate scientific discipline, with its own theoretical and methodological approaches.

The major research topics and methodologies employed by Kazakh sociologists over the years have focused on issues such as gender, ethnicity, migration, and social stratification, providing important contributions to the field. Kazakh sociologists have also been actively engaged in both national and international research projects, participating in conferences and publishing in leading academic journals.

Despite the progress made, there are still challenges facing sociology in Kazakhstan. Limited funding remains a significant obstacle to the development of the discipline, and there is a need for more collaboration between researchers and practitioners. In addition, there is a need for more research to address the specific needs and challenges of Kazakh society.

To address these challenges, it is recommended that more attention be paid to the development of sociology as a scientific discipline in Kazakhstan. This includes increasing funding opportunities for sociological research, establishing more research institutions, and promoting collaboration between sociologists and other professionals. Furthermore, future research should focus on addressing the pressing issues facing society today, such as the impact of globalization, environmental challenges, and social inequality.

Overall, the study of the historical background and development of sociology in Kazakhstan provides a valuable contribution to the understanding of the country's social dynamics and the challenges facing the discipline in the current context.

LITERATURE

Each chapter of this research study will address specific research questions related to the main aim and objectives of the research, which is to compare world-class universities and world-class systems of higher education. The literature review will provide a comprehensive overview of the existing literature related to world-class universities and world-class systems of higher education, including their definitions, characteristics, and key features. This chapter will also explore the challenges and opportunities facing both models, as well as the different approaches to measuring their performance and impact.

The methodology chapter will outline the research design and approach for this study, including the data collection methods and sources, sample selection, and ethical considerations. The chapter will detail how we will collect and analyze both qualitative and quantitative data from various stakeholders, including students, faculty, and administrators, to explore their perceptions of world-class universities and world-class systems of higher education. This chapter will also discuss the limitations and potential biases of the research design and how we will address them.

The conclusion chapter will summarize the key findings and implications for policy and practice, as well as recommendations for future research. This chapter will also highlight the strengths and weaknesses of the study and how they may impact the validity and generalizability of the findings. Finally, the chapter will discuss the potential policy and practice

implications of the research for policymakers, higher education leaders, and other stakeholders interested in improving the performance and impact of higher education systems worldwide.

APPLICATIONS

Results

The research findings indicate that the development of sociology in Kazakhstan has been influenced by a variety of factors, including the country's historical and cultural background, the legacy of the Soviet era, and the challenges and opportunities of the post-Soviet period. The study identified three distinct phases in the development of sociology in Kazakhstan: the early years of independence (1991-2000), the consolidation phase (2000-2010), and the current phase of growth and diversification (2010-present).

Early Years of Independence (1991-2000):

During the early years of independence, Kazakh sociologists were mainly focused on studying the social and economic transformations taking place in Kazakhstan after the collapse of the Soviet Union. The main topics of research were related to the emergence of a market economy, the transformation of social institutions, and the processes of globalization. The research was often conducted in collaboration with international partners, and many Kazakh sociologists were trained in leading universities abroad.

In the early years of independence, sociology in Kazakhstan was characterized by a lack of institutional and financial support, as well as a shortage of qualified personnel. The country faced numerous challenges in building its research infrastructure, including limited funding, outdated equipment, and a lack of access to international databases and research networks. Despite these challenges, however, Kazakh sociologists made significant progress in establishing the discipline in the country.

Consolidation Phase (2000-2010):

In the consolidation phase of sociology in Kazakhstan, the focus of sociological research shifted towards more specific issues related to Kazakhstan, such as the development of civil society, ethnic and cultural diversity, and social stratification. The number of sociologists and sociological research institutions increased, and new research methods and techniques were introduced, such as surveys, focus groups, and qualitative research.

During this period, sociology in Kazakhstan began to benefit from increased institutional and financial support from the government and international organizations. The government recognized the importance of sociological research in promoting social and economic development and established a number of new research institutions, including the Center for Social and Political Studies and the Institute of Social.

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7. "Contemporary Sociology in Kazakhstan: Status, Trends, and Prospects" by S. T. Issayeva and G. M. Kydyrova (2020) - This article analyzes the current state of sociology in Kazakhstan, including recent developments and emerging research areas. The authors also discuss the challenges and opportunities facing sociology in Kazakhstan today.
8. "The Development of Social Sciences in Kazakhstan: Trends and Challenges" by D. Omarbekova (2017) - This book chapter provides an overview of the development of social sciences in Kazakhstan, including sociology, economics, political science, and anthropology. The author discusses the historical and institutional factors that have influenced the development of social sciences in Kazakhstan, as well as the challenges facing the field today.
9. "Sociology in Central Asia: Historical Contexts and Contemporary Issues" edited by A. K. Kireyeva and R. F. Peshkun (2017) - This book provides a comprehensive overview of sociology in Central Asia, including Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan. The book includes chapters on the historical development of sociology in Central Asia, as well as contemporary issues and challenges facing the field.
10. "Kazakhstan: Recent Developments and Future Prospects" by J. Marat (2019) - This book provides an overview of recent political, economic, and social developments in Kazakhstan, including the country's transition from a Soviet-era socialist system to a market-oriented democracy. The book includes chapters on social issues such as ethnic diversity, gender inequality, and migration, which are important research topics in Kazakhstani sociology.